

Constraint Equations Leading to function * 1/function Terms in Various Equilibrium Scenarios?

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Equilibrium is often associated with a lack of change of some features in time. This, however, seems to imply that certain constraints are present. In some cases, these constraints may actually be associated with motion in time. Here we consider three different scenarios which we suggest describe equilibrium scenarios. We try to show that all of these have a constraint type equation of the form: $0 = \sum_i \text{function}(a_i) \dot{a}_i$ such that $\dot{a}_i = 1/\text{function}(a_i)$. The first scenario is a classical particle moving in a circle with constant speed. The first is a master equation for a simple two state system described in (1). The third is a special relativistic treatment of a particle with constant velocity in one dimension. We argue that in all cases a $\dot{a}_i = 1/\text{function}$ appears and suggest that free particle quantum mechanics arises by treating constant velocity motion in special relativity as a kind of equilibrium.

Equilibrium and Constraints

Equilibrium is often associated with certain variables which do not change in time. This implies a kind of constraint in the system, we argue, but different systems have different constraints. In fact, such a constraint may actually be associated with motion (change in time) of a vector. We suggest, however, that there seems to be a pattern in which one finds:

$$0 \text{ change} = \sum_i \text{function}(a_i) \dot{a}_i \text{ such that } \dot{a}_i = 1/\text{function}(a_i) \quad ((1))$$

We argue that this approach treats different terms in ((1)) in an independent (or equal footing) sense. We consider three examples. (Note, one does not necessarily need \dot{a}_i as a differential in ((1)), One could have the product of two functions: $\sum_i b_i a_i$ such that $\dot{a}_i = 1/b_i$ in order to place all terms on the same footing. Also to have 0 on the LHS, one needs a balance of plus and minus signs, but here we focus on the magnitude of a_i or \dot{a}_i .

A Classical Particle Moving with Constant Speed in a Circle

We suggest that a particle moving at a constant speed be considered as a kind of equilibrium situation in the sense that there are constant variables in the system. This does not mean that all variables are constant, only some. Even an ideal gas has particles which move about and collide, but density, pressure, temperature etc are constant in time.

A classical particle moving at constant speed in a circle involves both constant variables and variables changing in time. Some constant variables include:

- (A) Classical kinetic energy pp^2/m ,
- (B) $|p|$ magnitude of momentum
- (C) Magnitude of speed
- (D) Radius of the circle

Variables which change in time include: x, y, v_x, v_y and p_x, p_y , but these are subject to a constraint such that one has the constant variables A-D. This leads to a constraint linking changing variables to constant ones. One example is:

$$r^2 = \text{magnitude squared} = \text{constant} = \text{equilibrium variable} = x^2 + y^2 \quad ((2))$$

Mathematically, one knows that $x=r \cos(\omega t)$ and $y=r \sin(\omega t)$ ((3)), but we suggest considering only ((2)) and writing:

$$0 = x dx + y dy \quad ((4))$$

If the variables x and y are to be treated on the same footing, then we argue that there is a general principle suggesting that $|dx| = 1/x$ and $|dy|=1/y$. Now, to get 0, either dx or dy must be negative, but if they are on the same footing, both solutions (positive dx and negative dx) must be possible physically. This suggests two kinds of rotation, clockwise and counterclockwise.

Thus, $dx=b/x$ and $dy=b/y$ where b has to be determined. ((5))

Using ((3)), one has: $dx= \pm b(t) / (r \cos(\omega t))$ and $dy= b(t)/(r \sin(\omega t))$ ((6)) where $b(t)$ is an unknown function.

As well as: $dx= -r\omega \sin(\omega t) dt$ and $dy = r\omega \cos(\omega t) dt$

Thus, $b= dt r r \sin(\omega t)\cos(\omega t)$. The approach of ((5)) may appear to be a little artificial, but one may see the same mathematics appearing in the next example.

Master Equation for a Two Level System

(1) introduces two simple master equations for a non-equilibrium two level system: Here $p_1(t)$ is the probability for a particle to be in level p_1 at time t and $p_2(t)$ has a similar meaning. Then from (1):

$$dp_1/dt = -a_1 p_1 + a_2 p_2 \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad dp_2/dt = a_1 p_1 - a_2 p_2 \quad ((6b))$$

For equilibrium, one requires $dp_1/dt=dp_2/dt=0$ and so one has two equations of the form ((1))

Our approach is to suggest solutions of $p_1=b/a_1$ and $p_2=b/a_2$ again so that terms in a sum are of equal weight. One may then also use the constraint:

$$P_1 + p_2 = 1 \text{ so that: } b(1/a_1+1/a_2)=1 \text{ or } b(a_1+a_2)/(a_1 a_2) = 1 \text{ so: } b= a_1 a_2/(a_1+a_2)$$

$$\text{Then: } p_1= a_2/(a_1+a_2) \text{ and } p_2= a_1/(a_1+a_2) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is the solution of (1). In (1), a_1 is set to $\exp(-E_1/T)$ and a_2 to $\exp(-E_2/T)$.

As a result, we stress that one again sees a constraint equation of the form $0 = \sum_i a_i p_i$ and treats each term as independent and containing the same information and so $a_1 p_1$ should have the same magnitude as $a_2 p_2$. Otherwise there is a bias and non-equilibrium.

The Case of a Free Particle in Special Relativity

Whether one has special relativity or not, $x=vt$ for constant v in one dimension. ((8))

As a result, one would not really consider x and t as independent. Special relativity, however, does formally treat them as separate components of a vector (x, ct) implying a priori an independent form.

We start with the key assumption that any free particle represents an equilibrium type of system and seek a constraint form ((2)).

We begin with the one dimensional Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((9))$$

Here E and p are constants (functions of v) and $x=vt$ so $A(t)$, i.e changes at each trajectory point. As a result, $A(t)$ is not a constant which would describe an equilibrium, it seems. One may, however, write ((9)) as:

$$A_1 = 0 = -E dt + p dx \quad ((10))$$

In such a case, one has a form like ((2)) and one may suggest that E and p are independent variables (which is physically the case because they describe different interactions) so:

$$dt = \text{constant}/E \quad ((11a)) \quad \text{and} \quad x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((11b))$$

(Note: p describes impulse hits while E is linked to the distance traveled in a repulsive field. Two particles with the same p may yield the same impulse, but have different E values.)

If one really has an equilibrium, one should have a probability in x, t , i.e. $P(x, t)$ such that dx and dt are mixed by ((11)). If one wishes this probability to be constant to indicate equilibrium, then:

$$dP = 0 = dP/dx \text{ partial constant}/p + dP/dt \text{ partial constant}/E \quad ((12))$$

Here we do not use the trajectory $x=vt$, but rather the equilibrium dx and dt values of ((11)).

$$((12)) \text{ implies that: } P = \exp(-Et + px) \quad ((13))$$

Thus, the quantum free particle wavefunction appears as an equilibrium complex probability linked with two variables E and p .

We suggest that the formalism of the three equilibrium type examples are the same and that idea of function $\cdot 1/\text{function}$ seems to appear in all in order to make terms in a constraint equation with 0 on the LHS carry the same weight.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that an equilibrium scenario suggests that there exists some kind of constraint equation in place. We seek one of the form: $\text{change}=0 = \text{Sum over } i \text{ function}(a_i) da_i$ and argue that if a_i terms are independent and of the same footing each summand should have the same value suggesting that $da_i = 1/\text{function}(a_i)$. (More generally, one could have $\text{Sum over } i b_i a_i$ such that $a_i=1/b_i$.)

We consider three equilibrium type scenarios in which this occurs. The first is a particle moving in a circle with constant speed, the second is the master equation for a two level system given in (1) and the third is the description of a particle moving at constant v in one dimension in special relativity. We argue that treating the last example as an equilibrium case and using the function, $1/\text{function}$ approach leads to $P(x)=\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, i.e the free particle quantum wavefunction.

References

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